

Space Law and Space Security: National & International Challenges and Opportunities

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ABSTRACT:

With every aspect of space-related technology in a climactic development phase, and with all the more actors being either interested to or already engaged in space exploration and the exploitation of capabilities the Space provides in various sectors of human activity, it is high time that robust and up-to-date legal and policy frameworks be developed, in a national and international level. The continuous rise of opportunities that space exploration provides is driving humanity in new space race, this time with governmental and non-governmental actors, and technologies hitherto unfathomable. This situation is certain to provoke security risks in various levels, and especially those linked with nations' defense and security. This essay will attempt to encapsulate the basis of existing regulation regarding the Space domain, and furthermore approach security and military-centered issues with a combined legal and policy approach. Finally, a short and specific focus will be given to the Greek and European general policies that constellate with these issues, in an attempt to highlight risks and possibilities for a stable space policy in the near future.

Keywords:

space law; space security; space militarization; outer space treaty; space debris; anti-satellite weapons; esa; Greek space policy; liability; space objects; unoosa

I. Introduction

Space law is a complex system that governs activities in outer space. It consists of various components such as international treaties, conventions, United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) resolutions, as well as rules and regulations of international organizations (Lyll & Larsen, 2020). For Greece, as member of the European Union, and a partner of the European

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Space Agency, a lot of opportunities and challenges arise as per the Space exploration and utilization in general, and its Security related aspects in particular.

This article will explore the fundamental legal framework of Space Law on an international level, examining significant documents such as the Outer Space Treaty of 1967 [UN, 1967]. Additionally, the article will investigate the militarization of outer space by analyzing the intersection between space law and the evolving military activities occurring there [Giannopapa et al., 2015].

The legal framework of space law consists of five international treaties and five sets of principles that govern outer space [UN, 2002]. The UNGA resolutions and the UN Committee on the Peaceful Uses of Outer Space (COPUOS) documents serve as subsidiary means for interpreting and applying these treaties and principles [Cheng, 1997]. In addition, customary international law also plays a crucial role in shaping space law.

II. Treaties of the United Nations

The Outer Space Treaty of 1967

The Outer Space Treaty (OST) of 1967 is a pivotal legal instrument that established the foundation of the framework for space exploration. It stipulates that outer space, including the Moon and other celestial bodies, shall be used exclusively for peaceful purposes. However, the term "peaceful purposes" has been subject to interpretation, as space technology can serve both civilian and military functions. The treaty explicitly prohibits the placement of nuclear weapons or other weapons of mass destruction in orbit, on celestial bodies, or stationing them in outer space in any other manner. Notably, while the OST bans weapons of mass destruction, it does not entirely prohibit the weaponization of space, leaving room for the deployment of conventional weapons. Additionally, the treaty forbids any claims of sovereignty over the Moon and other celestial bodies, mandates that states are responsible for national space activities whether conducted by governmental or non-governmental entities, and holds states liable for damages caused by their space objects. All parties agree to conduct outer space activities in accordance with international law [UNOOSA].

The sum of these two provisions allows for certain specific conclusions relating to Security matters in Space. Firstly, there is practical and legal room for states to move military-scale security policies they already implement into the Space dimension, therefore broadening the spectrum of National Defense and National Security. Secondly, following the first conclusion, states can viably develop their military and security capabilities in Space, with dual and singular-use technologies. Furthermore, the liability (or *responsibility*) provisions described above mean that all of these capabilities require strict and robust safety frameworks, in both practical and legal levels. Hence, it can be said that Space Security will determine National Security capabilities in a structural level, in the very near future.

The Rescue Agreement

The *Agreement on the Rescue of Astronauts, the Return of Astronauts, and the Return of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, commonly known as *the Rescue Agreement*, was adopted in 1968. This treaty obligates signatories to take all possible measures to assist astronauts in distress and ensure their safe return to the launching state. It also covers the recovery and return of space objects that land outside the territory of the launching state. In the context of militarization, if astronauts (or any other military-grade personnel) were to engage in hostilities during wartime, they would lose the protections afforded by the Rescue Agreement and be considered prisoners of war under international humanitarian law [Space Foundation].

The Registration Convention

The *Convention on Registration of Objects Launched into Outer Space*, known as the *Registration Convention*, entered into force in 1976. This treaty builds upon Article VIII of the OST and establishes a mechanism for identifying space objects. It requires states to furnish information to the United Nations about the orbit of each space object, including its general function, thereby enhancing transparency and accountability in space activities [UConn].

The Moon Agreement

The *Agreement Governing the Activities of States on the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, or *the Moon Agreement*, was adopted in 1979. This treaty stipulates that the Moon and other celestial bodies must be used exclusively for peaceful purposes, and their environments should not be disrupted. It also requires that any stations established on these bodies must be reported to the United Nations. However, the Moon Agreement has limited legal effect due to the small number of signatory states, as major space-faring nations have not ratified it [UNOOSA].

The Liability Convention

The *Convention on International Liability for Damage Caused by Space Objects*, or the *Liability Convention* entered into force in September 1972, and is based on Article VII of the OST. As described in the UNOOSA official webpage, “the Liability Convention provides that a launching State shall be absolutely liable to pay compensation for damage caused by its space objects on the surface of the Earth or to aircraft, and liable for damage due to its faults in space” [UNOOSA]. The treaty directly allocates full liability for damages caused by any kind of space object – whether belonging to a governmental or non-governmental entity – that happens on the ground of the Earth or in the air (within the atmosphere), while on the other hand it maintains a *proof-of-fault* liability regime for damages that happen in space. The treaty is meant to provide a legal tool for any liability claim through a state-to-state mechanism, and also making a *Claims Commission* available as a forum if direct diplomatic options fail. It is also important to stress that developments in the AI realm manifest new challenges on the existing liability regime, as the *strict-liability* and/or *fault-based liability*

regimes are themselves redefined by the technological leaps of AI, with impending implications in Space as well.

III. Conventional International Law

Customary international law plays a pivotal role in shaping the legal framework governing outer space activities. The development of *jus cogens* norms, or peremptory principles recognized as fundamental to the international community, is inherently challenging in the context of outer space [Oralova, 2015]. Such principles often emerge from consistent state practices and the jurisprudence of international courts, reflecting global public interest and moral imperatives.

The foundation of current outer space law is anchored in global public interest, as articulated in Article I of the Outer Space Treaty (OST). This article emphasizes that Outer Space shall be free for exploration and use by all states, reinforcing principles such as the non-appropriation of Outer Space, sovereign equality, freedom of use, and the prohibition of nuclear weapons and weapons of mass destruction in outer space [UNOOSA]. These principles are often regarded as having customary international law status due to their widespread acceptance and consistent application.

A core tenet of customary international law in space is the utilization of outer space for peaceful purposes. This principle underscores the importance of non-aggression and the demilitarization of outer space, advocating for cooperative and harmonious use for the collective benefit of all nations. It actively discourages hostile or military endeavors beyond Earth's atmosphere [Oralova, 2015]. Recognized *jus cogens* principles in outer space law encompass the exploration and use of outer space for the benefit of all peoples, freedom of exploration and use, and the prohibition of national appropriation.

IV. A Synopsis of Space Military Operations

As space technology advances and more nations acquire capabilities in space, the potential for tension and conflict, particularly in military applications, increases. Historically, space has been utilized for military purposes, with early space-age militaries employing space technologies for intelligence, surveillance, and reconnaissance. Today, space has evolved into a distinct strategic domain, rendering military assets vulnerable to various forms of targeting. This evolving landscape has led some to argue that conflict in space is inevitable, prompting nations to seek protection for their space assets and posing threats to those of their adversaries. This intensified competition risks escalating tensions and conflicts in space, underscoring the urgent need for updated legal regulations to address emerging challenges and actors.

Despite significant advancements in space technology, the regulatory framework governing space activities has not kept pace. Since the adoption of the Moon Agreement in 1979, there has been a noticeable absence of specific treaties addressing the military aspects

of space endeavors or regulating potential inter-country tensions in the event of a conflict. Consequently, while outer space lacks national sovereignty and falls beyond national jurisdiction, it should not be perceived as a lawless frontier. The Outer Space Treaty (OST) of 1967 remains a cornerstone of space law; however, its applicability to contemporary military, civilian, and commercial space activities is constrained, given its origins during the Cold War era with a focus on state-centric space endeavors. Article IV of the OST prohibits the placement of nuclear weapons or any other kinds of weapons of mass destruction in orbit, on celestial bodies, or stationing them in outer space in any other manner [UNOOSA]. It also mandates that the Moon and other celestial bodies shall be used exclusively for peaceful purposes, forbidding the establishment of military bases, installations, fortifications, the testing of any type of weapons, and the conduct of military maneuvers on celestial bodies.

Recent developments further highlight the evolving nature of military operations in space. For instance, the U.S. Space Force has observed China conducting satellite maneuvers that mimic aerial combat, resembling dogfighting tactics in space. These activities involve synchronized movements of multiple objects in geostationary orbit, indicating offensive drills and challenging existing international norms [Turner, 2025]. Such actions underscore the pressing need for an updated and comprehensive legal framework to effectively address the militarization of space and ensure its peaceful use for the benefit of all humankind.

V. Space Security & Military issues

The militarization of space has raised significant concerns regarding the absence of clear laws and regulations governing military activities in outer space. This ambiguity has led to inconsistent and overlapping policies, creating operational and legal challenges due to the intertwining of military and civilian interests. As space technology advances and national security considerations intensify, the issues of space weaponization and the potential for armed conflict in outer space have become increasingly pressing [Joyce, 2024]. It is crucial to distinguish between *space militarization* — the use of space resources to support and enhance military capabilities — and *space weaponization*, which involves the development and deployment of weapons intended to target objects in outer space.

The lack of clear definitions for specific terms and scenarios in space law poses significant challenges. While principles governing the use of force and the laws of armed conflict (LOAC) apply to space activities, their application to military acts in space is not always clear due to the distinct nature of the space environment. For example, assessing proportionality in the vastness of space and addressing potential collateral damage, such as debris impacting other satellites, present unique difficulties [Berrang, 2023].

Establishing a comprehensive and well-defined legal framework for space law is crucial to resolving conflicts and preventing the use of force in outer space. This framework should adhere to international law, extending the reach of established legal principles into outer space. Integrating the modern laws of armed conflict with space law can promote the

peaceful and responsible use of outer space while mitigating the risks associated with potential conflicts in this increasingly contested domain [Rozpedowski, 2024].

Meanwhile, research into the legal issues surrounding armed conflicts in outer space is crucial due to the profound potential impact such conflicts could have on the rule of law. The use of ground-based or space-based weapons in outer space is considered a "use of force" under international law. The United Nations (UN) Charter, established before the space age, serves as a fundamental component of the global legal framework and is applicable to all realms of international law, including space law. Various international instruments have been adapted over time to accommodate evolving contexts and technological advancements, justifying the incorporation of the UN Charter into matters concerning outer space [UNIDIR, 2024].

The Outer Space Treaty (OST) of 1967, a cornerstone of space law, does not explicitly regulate the application of the right to self-defense in outer space. However, Article 51 of the UN Charter recognizes the inherent right of individual or collective self-defense if an armed attack occurs against a member state. This right is not confined to terrestrial domains and extends to outer space, allowing states to defend their space assets. The exercise of self-defense in outer space must comply with the principles of necessity and proportionality, ensuring that any defensive measures are appropriate and not excessive in response to the threat posed. The lack of explicit prohibitions in both general international law and space law regarding self-defense in outer space implies that spacefaring nations retain this right. Denying the right to self-defense in outer space could place these nations at a disadvantage in safeguarding national security and pursuing their interests in the space domain. Therefore, it is widely accepted that international legal norms do not prohibit asserting the right to self-defense in outer space [UNOOSA].

Given all of the above, severe contemporary challenges involving military issues can be traced in three sectors where cutting-edge technology is about to meet possible space militarization: a) regulation and use of anti-satellite (ASAT) weapons, b) space debris issues, and c) autonomous (AI-powered) space objects:

- The ASAT weapons are weapons or weapon systems specifically designed to target and destroy satellites, with the use of kinetic energy, high-intensity lasers and/or nuclear technology, and can be launched from ground, sea, air and space. While the OST may prohibit the use of nuclear and mass-destruction weapons in-orbit, conventional ASAT weapons cannot be put directly under its strict restriction. Even the *peaceful purposes* relative provisions cannot override the UN Charter's Article 51 provision on a nation's right to self-defense, hence rendering any discussion about conventional ASAT weapons one based on the result of any possible use, and not on precaution (e.g. prohibition of development). The PRC's 2007 ASAT weapons testing, for example, proved that existing regulation is far from capable of actively regulating the sector, and also created a chain of issues linked directly with environmental sustainability and – the below mentioned – *space debris* [Schellekens, 2008] It is also important to stress that any action against the earth-

based components of ASAT weapon systems cannot be directly linked with Space Law provisions, and it is more likely to befall within the scope of the UN Charter's self-defense provisions.

- Space Debris issues are also becoming an increasingly important domain of legal and practical discourse, related to the rapid multiplication of human-made objects set in orbit in the recent decades, as well as the possibility of accidents or active conflict happening in space, that would create large amounts of uncontrollable debris. The OST in general seems rather outdated to face such challenges. On the other hand, Article IX of the OST specifically, may provide its “due regard” obligation¹ and the “no harm” principle² in combination, as a tool to allocate accountability appropriately in states, and entities functioning under these states' authority. However, it should be noted that the current framework is in definite need of remodeling, in order to respond to these contemporary challenges [Radi, 2023].
- The rapid development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in every sector of the world's economies is also evident in the Space sector. AI-powered space objects operate independently, enhancing capabilities in any kind of task, including military applications. Hence, the whole legal framework concerned with the Space domain applies – or better, needs to apply – in autonomous space objects, and specifically military and security-focused assets. Furthermore, AI-powered space objects have a direct legal linkage with liability issues that have yet to be determined internationally, such as determination of the “fault” in AI systems or “gross negligence”, and so produce troubles in applying strict legal rules.

These three contemporary legal and policy issues are indicative of the gaps that the age and simplicity of the already existing Space Law frameworks, and further stress out the need for new and innovative approaches.

VI. An example of forming innovative legal structures

In the realm of space exploration, significant strides are being made to establish regulations governing military operations in outer space. A pivotal development in this area is the *Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations*. Although it does not represent a strict and robust legal framework and its applicability is restricted to those willing to apply it, this comprehensive guide articulates legal principles applicable to military activities in space, addressing critical issues such as the definition of outer space and the criteria for peaceful purposes [Beard & Stephens, 2024]. Its primary aim is to provide clear

¹ All state parties are mandated to take into account the interests of other states with *due regard* while they conduct their space activities.

² All state parties carry the obligation to conduct exploration of outer space so as to avoid its harmful contamination and, where necessary, to adopt appropriate measures.

and comprehensive guidance for decision-makers involved in space activities, promoting peace and security in outer space.

The Woomera Manual is structured to mirror national military manuals, enhancing its utility as a reference for military operators and decision-makers. However, its role has sparked ongoing debates regarding its impact on space warfare. Some scholars and practitioners question whether the manual serves to constrain or inadvertently legitimize warfare in space. These discussions are crucial, as they influence how the manual is perceived and applied within the broader context of international law and military strategy. In summary, the Woomera Manual represents a significant effort to codify existing international law as it pertains to military operations in space. While it provides valuable clarity and guidance, its influence on the conduct of space warfare continues to be a subject of active discussion and analysis.

VII. Challenges and Opportunities entangled with Space Security for Greece (and the EU)

7.1 Greece

Given all of the above, as well as recent developments in technology, a multiplicity of challenges and opportunities arise for all actors aiming to participate in this new age of Space Exploration. Greece, both for itself as a state and as a member-state of the European Union, may prove to be increasingly involved with space activities.

Such activities will put National Defense and Security at the forefront of Greek interest, as is also suggested by the relevant proposition made by the Hellenic Space Center to the competent governmental authorities in 2021, which, though, was just a first attempt in a policy proposal that has yet to develop into a robust National Space Policy framework. In this first proposition, the Center referred to the sector of national defense and civil protection, and their boosting, as the prime pillar of a newfound Greek National Space Policy and Strategic Action Plan. It is, as such, proposed – among other actions – that the Greek administration should have a cohesive management plan for all Greek space activity (private and public), so as to safeguard national interests and achieve a sustainable and secure environment for the nation's involvement in the sector. Furthermore, developing and enhancing European Space Agency (ESA) involvement is also deemed essential.

Greece has recently moved on to a more aspiring approach on space activity, with its involvement with the *National SmallSat Program* (backed by the ESA, PlanetScope and the Greece 2.0 Recovery and Resilience Fund), with strong applications in sectors such as natural disaster prevention, e.g. with the acquirement of several Earth observation microsatellites by 2026, and management and (possibly) military-wise situational awareness in the Balkan Peninsula and Eastern Mediterranean [*National SmallSat Program*, 2023]. Also, another recent and more strategic Greek initiative led to Greece becoming a main hub of the GOVSATCOM and IRIS programs, which – among others – aim to establishing secure satellite telecommunication for all of Europe, and also partner with NATO [HUFFPOST, 2025]. Such

initiatives indicate that Greece is centered on a developing and upscaling role in its space policy, keeping national security and defense pillars at the forefront. It is visible, however, that all these undertakings are at a rather nascent level, and any activity related especially with the more military issues stressed within this essay is, as of yet, only in theory level.

In any cases, Greece has to take in serious regard that any and all of these initiatives require both a strong commitment and integration with the relevant European frameworks and agencies, and serious financial resources. Especially in the financial field, the strong integration with European projects and organizations involved with space exploration and security may amplify the country's capabilities, by securing co-funding from European resources, rather than the limited national ones. Of course, in any occasion, it is essential that there exists care for balancing integration with the European industry with developing the national economy and relevant market. Else arises a strong risk of short-term policy limitation and sectorial stagnation, that Greece cannot afford if it chooses – as one can say it should – to actually invest in this domain that can play a pivotal and multifaceted role in national security and defense.

7.2 European Union

As per the EU as a whole, although it has, as of yet, maintained a more economy-orientated approach for its general space activity development, all of the above, including Greek initiatives, may prove increasingly important for Europe as a whole in the coming years. Systems such as *Galileo* and *EGNOS* may become vital for European security, and this fact is directly linked with Greek interests as well.

The two basic pillars of EU space activity are the *European Space Agency (ESA)* and the *European Union Agency for the Space Program (EUSPA)*.

- The ESA is an European intergovernmental organization established in 1975, and comprised of 23 member-states (incl. Norway and Switzerland), focusing on space research and technological development, and burdened with designing and developing space infrastructure, operational and technical expertise. It aims to promote European strategic autonomy in all aspects of space exploration and providing a safe and secure space infrastructure and technology for European partners [ESA, 2025].
- The EUSPA is an agency of the EU, established in 2021, and tasked with operational management of the EU's space program. Its activity is regulated by the 2021/696 Regulation of the EU, and it involves the operation of programs such as *Galileo*, *GOVSATCOM* and *EGNOS*, with a specified oversight. It is important to refer to the Financial Framework Partnership Agreement (between ESA, EUSPA and the European Commission) of 2021, specifically allocates responsibilities and authorities between the three related bodies, and creates the necessary framework for their financial and operational functionality [EUSPA, 2025].

The EU, in the contemporary fluid geostrategic environment, is definite to be required to enhance its military and security capabilities in Space. In such regard, its large resources may

help for a quick – and necessary – leap in infrastructure and technology development. Along with that, EU member-states' strong engagement in all relevant international organizational may prove a vital tool in shaping the frameworks with due regard to European interests, especially in fields such as autonomous space objects and space debris. In more strictly security matters, a conjunction with the rest of the NATO partners, particularly the USA, is also essential to achieving sustainable and viable solutions that safeguard both its people's interests and liberties, and at the same time guaranteeing their protection from military nature threats.

In general, it can be concluded that dual-use technologies, with their research and development, will probably play an increasingly important role in shaping Greece's and the EU's space policies. All competent authorities should therefore make sure to develop a thorough understanding of all the abovementioned frameworks and challenges, and also pioneer in multiplying national and European engagement in all relevant discussions and activities internationally. No serious future security planning and undertaking can be carried out without guaranteeing a robust Space Security approach.

VIII. Conclusion

In conclusion, for a robust modern policy framework, coupled with its legal twin, to exist functionally, either for a country such as Greece or for any kind of national, private and international entity, and with a special focus on sustainable security, it is essential to re-evaluate international law concerning space activities, focusing on the right to self-defense in space. The outdated United Nations space treaties are inhibiting progress in the face of a rapidly expanding internationalized space economy. Urgent action is needed to create clear rules protecting national security, and security-related interests, while encouraging international collaboration. As we navigate the complexities of space law, it is crucial to collaborate and form policies that ensure the safety and success of future space activities. The international society must work together to create a framework that balances the interests of spacefaring states, while fostering the responsible use of outer space for the benefit of all, with Greece and the EU having to understand the importance and the required rapidity that all this work requires, and also making sure to secure a leading and active role in such.

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SHORT BIOS

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